

The Realities of E-government in the South African Local Government: Are We Moving from Access to Inequality?

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In recent years, public administration has increasingly shifted toward the digitalisation of government services to enhance both administrative efficiency and service delivery. In line with this global trend, many governments, including the South African government, have adopted digital initiatives to improve their efficiency and the quality of services provided. During this movement, numerous challenges have arisen, and while earlier research has largely concentrated on these issues, it has paid comparatively less attention to whether e-government initiatives improve access or exacerbate inequality. This paper closes the gap by expanding the literature on how e-government initiatives can contribute to inequalities instead of fostering access to services. The paper is qualitative in nature and uses secondary data to address the questions, aims and objectives. The authors find that there are numerous elements, such as poor digital literacy, infrastructure, socio-economic issues, and political limitations. These elements hinder the abilities of communities in fully accessing e-government platforms and services. As such, the communities are not fully able to access e-government services, which indirectly translates to inequalities. The paper further demonstrates that communities in rural areas suffer the most in terms of accessing the e-government platforms and services. It is recommended that the local government function hand in hand with other levels of the government to ensure that e-government platforms and services are accessible to the communities. This is especially important in rural areas.

Keywords: E-government, e-services, inequality, access, South African municipalities

In recent years, public administration has moved towards digitalising public services to improve administrative efficiency and service delivery (Mphahlele, Kekwaletswe, & Seaba, 2025). This movement is known as e-government (electronic government). E-government, as advised by Muridzi (2019) exists to ensure wider access to government services and foster citizen engagement. In South Africa, well-known earlier researchers such as Visser and Twinomurizi (2008) stated that e-government was developed to enhance service delivery. Moreover, e-government is established promote the government's service delivery improvement technique, which is known as the Batho Pele and has the intention to put people first. In the same circumstances, other scholars added that e-government was also designed to provide access to government services and lessen corrupt practices (Nulhusna, Sandhyaduhita, Hidayanto, & Thusavat, 2017).

In this paper, we, as the authors, are of the view that e-government was designed to ensure that institutions of the government, especially the local government, give democratic and accountable governance to

their communities. This is to ensure service delivery as required by the 1996 Constitution of the Republic of South Africa. However, it is important to note that meeting the above constitutional obligations is difficult for municipalities in South Africa. Various public administration scholars portray this as indicating that municipalities are failing dismally to attain the constitutional goals (Mabeba, 2021; Enwereji & Uwizeyimana, 2020). The primary reasons for the above are fraud, corruption, poor governance, nepotism, political instability and interference, and mismanagement of municipal funds (Mabizela & Malinga, 2025). The failure to attain the constitutional goals because of the above means inadequate service delivery.

Scholars like Ragolane (2025) indicate that there has been a rise in service provision protests or rallies demanding improved services from 2004 to 2022 because of inadequate service delivery. These protests are still ongoing (Thusi & Ndebele, 2024). This shows the issues affecting municipalities in South Africa. E-government is established with the hope that it can attempt to resolve some of the issues causing inadequate service delivery. Moreover, it aims to improve the accessibility and efficiency of municipalities in providing services to the communities. Although this is the expectation, Agangiba and Kabanda (2016) believe that e-government experiences several issues within the South African municipalities. Some of these issues lead to unequal access to e-government services. As a result, such issues establish situations where some of the community members are able access e-government services while some are not able to. This raises a question as to whether e-government promotes access or inequality.

This has been a rhetorical question which scholars in public administration and management have been posing in their scholarly

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academic papers, questioning the accessibility of e-government services. This has been well-captured by studies such as Mohale (2024) and Nkgapele and Mokgolobotho (2024) acknowledging that e-government serves as a mechanism to improve service efficiency, but questions whether all members of the communities can access these services. This question has been neglected in the literature written on e-government in South Africa, particularly within the local government. From a theoretical perspective, Nulhusna et al. (2017) state that e-government reduces physical barriers to access and streamlines government operations. However, these e-government services are not fully accessible to all areas and all members of the community. This poses questions shown below:

- Who can avail themselves of these online services?
- Who can access these e-government services?
- Are they even accessible?

The problem emerging is that e-government services are being offered; however, these services are not easily accessible, especially within the local government. It must be well noted that the efficiency of these e-government services depends on their accessibility. This is due to the idea that e-government was established with the aim to improve service delivery in line with the Batho Pele principles. In these principles, one of the principles is "Access", of which the White Paper on Transforming Public Service Delivery (1997) states that all members of the communities must have equal access to services to which they are entitled. This simply means the principle of "Access" should be followed and promoted even in e-government

platforms. However, that is not the case in reality, as proven by Mohale (2024) stating that not all residents in each community can access e-government services. Earlier literature on e-government mainly explored conundrums experienced in the transition from traditional government to e-government, and less on clarifying whether e-government promotes access or exacerbates inequalities. This remains the gap in the literature that this current paper intends to address.

Method

In this paper, the authors deemed a qualitative approach as an appropriate methodology to examine the realities of e-government in South African local government. This approach was used to examine whether e-government promotes access to services or exacerbates inequalities. In doing so, secondary sources were utilised and only limited to academic journal articles, government reports, white papers, policy documents, and conference proceedings. The reason was to ensure that the secondary sources included in the paper are of high-quality and peer-reviewed. These sources were collected from search engines such as Google Scholar, Research Gate, and University Repositories. In searching for these sources, keywords such as e-government in South Africa, e-government services in local government and barriers to accessing e-government services were used. The authors followed an inclusion and exclusion criterion which is demonstrated in Table 1 below:

Table 1

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion	Exclusion
Studies focusing on the availability of e-government services in South African municipalities, considering socio-economic, infrastructure, and policy aspects	Studies that were not focused on e-government services in South African municipalities or digital access
Only publications written in English were considered because translation resources were limited.	Publications in languages other than English were not considered.
Studies published between 2019 and 2025	Studies published before 2019 were excluded.

The authors used a thematic content analysis to identify themes and patterns from the literature. This assisted the paper in organising findings and grouping them in categories, which speaks to the objective of the paper.

Results

Socio-Economic Inequalities

Socio-economic inequalities shape access to e-government services. Studies indicate that much of South Africa's population lacks the necessary financial resources to access and use e-government services (Masenya, 2021). With a 55.5% poverty rate, the expenses of internet, devices, and data pose formidable obstacles (Statistics South Africa, 2023). This shows that while e-government is intended to promote efficiency and accessibility, it risks widening the gap between affluent and impoverished groups, despite its aims of greater efficiency and reach. Moreover, location plays a role in driving disparities in e-government access (Nkgapele, 2024). South Africa's uneven spread of economic and developmental resources leaves rural areas underserved. Gilwald, Mothobi, and Rademan (2018) document how these communities face stunted development

and limited resources, yielding substandard living conditions, weak infrastructure, and scant connectivity. Compounding factors include residents' low education and income (Shibambu, 2024; Mofokeng, Ramolobe, & Bogopa, 2025). which severely hinders rural citizens' engagement with e-government platforms.

Molobela (2025) supports this view: the digital divide extends beyond unequal access to digital infrastructure or ICT. Rural communities often withdraw from online municipal engagements, reflecting lifestyle barriers. Education gaps compound the issue, curtailing low-income households' e-government participation (Nel-Sanders & Malomane, 2022). Only 55% of South African households accessed the internet in 2019 (African Union, 2020). Rural usage stood at just 36%, widening the divide (Statistics South Africa, 2023). Such low connectivity impedes e-government reliance on the internet, erecting barriers for rural and low-income citizens (Aruleba & Jere, 2022). Education and income correlate with resource access, including quality schooling and technology. Mohale (2024) identifies education as pivotal to socio-economic disparities in e-government use. In South Africa, quality education depends on location and socio-economic standing.

Rural and low-income learners often lack essential resources and infrastructure, yielding deficient education and digital literacy (Zindi, 2024). This impairs e-government use and curtails economic prospects, locking individuals into poverty and digital exclusion (Nel-Sanders & Malomane, 2022). Geographic location and socio-economic status dictate education levels, digital literacy, and internet use; low education thus sustains the digital divide, restricts e-government access, and reinforces South Africa's socio-economic disparities (Nokele & Mukonza, 2021). Statistics South Africa (2023) reveal the pattern: 41% of 20-24-year-olds lack a matric certificate, with tertiary attainment at just 22%. Rural poverty amplifies these gaps. The issue transcends individuals to become a societal challenge (Aruleba & Jere, 2022). Poor education and digital literacy stifle productivity and growth, impeding South Africa's advance toward the National Development Plan 2030 and a fairer society (Shibambu, 2024).

Infrastructure and Connectivity Challenges

South Africa's push to deliver efficient and fair public services through e-government is being undermined by obstacles that disproportionately affect rural and low-income communities (Mogale, 2024). E-government promises better delivery, transparency, and engagement (Butana & Niyitunga, 2024); however, it demands reliable infrastructure and connectivity (Mogale, 2021). Alfred Nzo District Municipality in the Eastern Cape exemplifies the shortfall: the absence of broadband stalls service rollout. OR Tambo District Municipality, in the old Transkei region, grapples with high rural density and scant broadband due to weak ICT foundations (Zindi, 2024). Sengu Local Municipality mirrors this for the rural poor, meager investment leaves the internet spotty (Aruleba & Jere, 2022). Residents struggle with online requests and engagement tools as a result (Mogale, 2021).

Unreliable connectivity and infrastructure compound barriers to e-government access, which broaden the digital divide and sustain socio-economic disparities (Apleni & Smuts, 2020). Reliable networks and infrastructure underpin e-government provision; their absence burdens rural and low-income municipalities, skewing the distribution of digital resources (Zindi, 2024). Rural communities thus struggle to reach vital information and services online. This gap fuels the digital divide: citizens without digital means are excluded from e-government entirely (Mesa, 2023; Mofokeng et al., 2025). Weak coverage also undermines data accuracy and feedback in citizen engagement, eroding governance efficacy and deepening inequalities (Masenya, 2021).

Digital Literacy

Digital literacy governs access to and effective use of e-government services (Nkgapele, 2024). Shibambu (2024) contends that rural and low-income citizens in South African municipalities cannot navigate these platforms absent requisite digital skills. This deficit in digital literacy presents a significant barrier to access and usability, which perpetuates existing inequalities in access to public services (Nel-Sanders & Malomane, 2022). Low digital literacy echoes through municipal service delivery. Citizens lacking skills cannot retrieve government information, file requests, or join engagement forums (Muridzi, 2019). Efficiency and transparency suffer as a result; frustration mounts and trust in institutions wanes. South Africa's elderly and poor swell the digitally illiterate ranks (Nel-Sanders & Malomane, 2022). Gilwald et al. (2018) report that just 36% of those

aged 60 and above possess basic digital skills.

Poor citizens lack the digital technologies and training opportunities needed to build skills, constrained by finances (Nel-Sanders & Malomane, 2022). This blocks e-government access. Low digital literacy affects not only citizens but also municipal staff tasked with the e-government rollout (Masenya, 2021). Apleni and Smuts (2020) highlight digital skills shortages across South Africa's public service, especially municipalities. Rural and low-income areas see staff falter on data analysis, online tools, and cybersecurity (Chohan & Guangwei, 2022). Employee deficits lead to service delays, degrade platform performance, and jeopardise data security. The Auditor General of South Africa (2022) noted that half of Eastern Cape municipalities want cybersecurity, leaving data vulnerable to attacks.

Administrative and Political Constraints

Political and administrative stakeholders shape e-government adoption, implementation, and use in South African municipalities. Thusi, Matyana, and Jilli (2023) highlight the benefits of e-government, yet administrative and political obstacles hinder them. Low institutional capacity, interdepartmental discord, and politics competing priorities, weak will, corruption, and divisions impede development, rollout, and usability of e-government (Enaifoghe et al., 2023). South Africa's post-1994 democratic shift spurred political and economic change. Infrastructure and economy advanced despite these gains. However, challenges remain prevalent in delivering services to citizens, particularly those in rural and low-income communities (Van der Waldt, 2023). Gaosekwe (2023) asserts that e-government has been identified as a potential tool to address these challenges.

However, implementing e-government services has faced several administrative and political challenges. In particular, the low levels of institutional capacity within municipalities (Auditor General of South Africa, 2022). A report by the South African Local Government Association (2022) shows that municipalities are challenged with low levels of institutional capacity due to the lack of skilled personnel, such as IT specialists, data analysts, and project managers, who are usually outsourced. Furthermore, evidence shows that municipalities are challenged with developing in-house talents and expertise, as there is a high turnover rate among skilled personnel, as seen in the City of Ekurhuleni, where over 10 qualified and experienced specialists in the field of Information Technology resigned in favour of jobs with better performing and equipped municipalities and private sector jobs. Beyond low institutional capacity, municipalities struggle with a lack of coordination between government departments and levels of government, which limits the usability and effectiveness of e-government services (City of Ekurhuleni, 2022). For instance, there is often a disconnect between national-level policies and local-level implementation, leading to duplication of efforts, fragmented services, and reduced efficiency (Nokele & Mukonza, 2022).

This lack of coordination is often compounded by the challenges of political differences between political parties in power at different levels of government, for example, Gauteng provincial government which is held by the African National Congress (ANC) and Midvaal local municipality which is led by the Democratic Alliance (DA) is often riddled by disputes over funding, policy direction and implementation of e-government services (Shibambu, 2024). On the other hand, in the process, municipalities face issues such as political

instabilities and a lack of political will as barriers to effective implementation and use of e-government services in South Africa (Thusi et al., 2023). Moreover, with the decentralized political system and fragmented political landscape, political instabilities are bound to happen. In addition, the national government developed several e-government enabling strategies, such as the NDP and e-Government strategy (Mohale, 2024). Due to political differences and instabilities, these strategies have faced challenges in coordination and implementation at the local government. For example, in municipalities such as the Uluudi local municipality, political leadership lacks the technical skills, expertise, and resources to implement e-government services (Muridzi, 2019). Political instabilities have severe effects on the implementation and usability of e-government services as they create room for challenges such as shifting and competing priorities by the political leadership, which impacts the budgetary allocations and processes, subsequently undermining long-term planning and implementation of e-government services, which leads to a lack of continuity and investment in e-government initiatives (Thusi & Selepe, 2023).

Aruleba and Jere (2022) posit that political instabilities create opportunities for corruption as officials take advantage of the uncertainty to engage in self-dealing and patronage. In the late 1990s, the government of South Africa committed to digital transformation, which was backed by the establishment of the Department of Public Service Administration and the State Information Technology Agency (Gaosekwe, 2023). Despite its potential, e-government remains largely unrealised due to insufficient political will. This insufficient political will is reflected in limited resource allocation, resistance to transparency and accountability, and weak institutional support for innovative and disruptive technologies (Thusi et al., 2023). Apleni and Smut (2020) argue that such resistance is often rooted in limited understanding, uncertainty, concerns about losing control over established processes, and the absence of clearly perceived benefits. These dynamics are evident in the City of Tshwane's implementation of an e-procurement portal for information sharing and tender submissions. Although intended to promote transparent procurement, the system encountered opposition from council leaders and administrative officials, largely driven by fears related to job security, loss of control over tender processes, and uncertainty surrounding the new system (Shibambu, 2024).

Privacy and Data Security Concerns

Digital technologies have revolutionised government-citizen interactions, delivering convenience and speed. However, heavier dependence on these systems stirs alarms over privacy and security for data held by public bodies (Van der Walddt, 2023). In South African municipalities, such worries block e-government uptake (Zindi, 2024). One of the primary concerns surrounding e-government services is the collection, storage, and use of personal and sensitive information (Mohale, 2024). Public service digitisation spurs agencies to amass vast data, including names, addresses, and financial details (Van der Walddt, 2023). Johannesburg's platform captures rates, property taxes, and service requests in this way (Cornelius & Van Rensburg, 2024). Lacking encryption, access controls, and regular audits (Mogale, 2021), these setups invite breaches and unauthorized access to citizen data.

Zindi (2024) warns that data breaches expose citizens' personal and financial details to cyberattacks, leading to identity theft, fraud,

and other forms of malicious activity, as in Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality. Such lapses defy data protection laws safeguarding privacy (South Africa Local Government Association, 2023). Municipalities like Johannesburg reveal poor encryption systems, feeble safeguards, and porous access controls, as evidenced by the 2021 Safe City initiative (Cornelius & Van Rensburg, 2024). E-government promised to streamline delivery and curb South Africa's inequalities (Nkgapele, 2024). Instead, it has deepened exclusion, widening socio-economic gaps and barring the vulnerable from vital services (Enaifoghe, Dlamini, Jili, & Mthethwa, 2023).

Discussion

Socio-economic Inequalities

In this paper, it was found that there are numerous impediments to accessing e-government services within the local government, especially in rural and remote areas. These impediments are poor digital literacy, infrastructure and connectivity limitations, socio-economic inequalities, privacy and data security concerns and administrative and political limitations. It must be noted that these impediments not only affect the accessibility of e-government services but also exacerbate socio-economic inequalities. This is because these impediments limit other members of the community from accessing services digitally. Which translate into a situation whereby fewer communities are able to access, while others are not able to access them, which creates inequalities. This situation is dire as socio-economic inequalities show wider social and economic issues in South Africa. This paper showed that socio-economic inequalities, such as education, geographic location as well as income levels, determine the accessibility of e-government services. This is because some services require, for example, mobile data. Someone from a low-income family might not be able to afford this to access these services. This implies that they are automatically excluded from accessing these e-services.

The paper also found that the digital divide acts as petrol to the fire, and by that we mean that it exacerbates inequalities even further and limits the ability of marginalised communities to access services. This is surprising, particularly in South Africa, where the government has committed to ensuring all members of the community can access government services through the Batho Principles. These principles, based on the 1997 White Paper on Transforming Public Service Delivery, the Batho Pele principles are as follows:

Figure 1

Batho Pele Principles

Note. Source: (Department of Public Service and Administration, 1997)

These principles should be adhered to even in e-government to

ensure the accessibility of e-services, administrative efficiency and transparency. E-government platforms should listen to communities and respond to their feedback. They should also provide clear and reliable information so that the government remains accountable. Although e-government was introduced to improve service delivery, in reality, it often benefits people who can afford internet data. Those who cannot afford data are left out and are unable to use online services. This situation goes against the Batho Pele principle of Access, because not everyone has equal access to municipal services. As a result, inequality is unintentionally increased. Employed community members who can afford data are able to access services online, while poorer residents still depend on paper-based systems. This contradicts the main goal of the National Development Plan (NDP), which aims to reduce inequality. It raises an important question: how can inequality be reduced if many communities do not have digital access to municipal services?

While the NDP seeks to reduce poverty and inequality, this can only be achieved if more people are employed and supported to rise above the poverty line. The government should therefore prioritise the creation of job opportunities, especially for people living in rural and remote areas. In addition, the government should consider providing free or subsidised monthly internet data to poor rural communities so that they can access e-government services. If community members are able to access municipal services online, they can also apply for jobs that are advertised digitally. This will allow more people to participate in online recruitment processes and help reduce the gap between the rich and the poor. Access to digital services also supports other Batho Pele principles. When communities can access municipal platforms, they can obtain information about local government and take part in consultations. This helps ensure that services provide value for money. The 1997 White Paper on Transforming Public Service Delivery states that when service standards are not met, communities should receive an apology, a clear explanation, and a quick solution. Complaints should be handled respectfully and positively. E-government platforms make it easier for municipalities to share this information with communities. Due to this, public trust in local government can be strengthened, supporting the Batho Pele principles of Openness and Transparency, Redress, Consultation, and Service Standards.

Infrastructure and Connectivity Challenges

The paper found that some of the factors hindering access to e-government services are a lack of infrastructure and poor connectivity, particularly in rural areas. It is worth noting that e-government was established to improve service delivery; however, its success depends on the technological infrastructure. That is because in the e-government era, services are accessed electronically through the use of technology. Some municipalities in rural areas of the Eastern Cape, such as Alfred Nzo, OR Tambo, and Sengu Local Municipality, struggle with technological infrastructure as well as internet connectivity. The paper has shown that such struggles limit the ability of communities to access public services electronically. Which, in other words, means that not all communities can access public services and also exercise “public participation”. This shows that even with the existence of the legislative frameworks and white papers advocating for equitable service delivery, other communities in rural areas remains side-lined in accessing services. This leaves these communities behind in the electronic transition. Again, this establishes a digital divide whereby

community members from rural areas are not able to access services and take part in governance processes. However, communities from urban areas are able to access services. This shifts the focus of e-government from promoting access to promoting inequalities. The government should look into investing more of its revenue in ICT, especially in rural areas, to avoid exacerbating inequalities in South Africa, as Mofokeng and Nkgapele (2025) and Nkgapele et al. (2025) regard it as a nation with inequalities.

Digital Literacy

The paper found that e-government requires both communities and government officials to be digitally literate. It has been found that there is a lack of digital skills amongst communities, which serves as a barrier for communities to take part in e-government. This issue is prevalent, particularly when it comes to old members of the communities who lack the resources, training and exposure to e-government platforms. Because of this, these community members are not able to access e-government services. This underscores the importance of communities receiving sufficient training to ensure they are digitally informed and can interact with e-government platforms. The same goes for public officials; they require training to fully interact with e-government. This is to ensure that both communities and the public officials can interact with e-government platforms. That is because the digital literacy gap worsens current issues of inequalities in service delivery.

Administrative and Political Constraints

The paper shows that e-government as a mechanism to improve service delivery is affected by organisational weaknesses as well as political limitations. Many municipalities in South Africa struggle with low capacity, which usually results in a lack of skilled talent, particularly in the fields of IT (Nkgapele et al., 2025). These shortages create outsourcing opportunities where municipalities outsource skills which are expensive to maintain. In the long run, they lead to elevated costs and constrained long-term capacity building. The other problem is elevated levels of turnover, as demonstrated by the City of Ekurhuleni, which undermined initiatives taken to create a stable and functional e-government operation. The findings also showed how a lack of political will worsens the conundrums of e-government initiatives. This is because of differences in political parties, which lead to inconsistent support and shifts in priorities, which create opportunities for corruption to thrive.

Privacy and Data Security Concerns

Privacy and data security concerns have been identified as issues in e-government, as it is documented that communities have less confidence in e-government. These occurrences, such as data breaches as well as unauthorised access to an individual's confidential information, can lead to malicious activities such as identity and financial fraud. This serves as a reason as to why members of the public are less interested in using e-government services, which leads to a lack of access compared to those who do have access. In other words, these issues further worsen current socio-economic inequalities and impede service delivery.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper showed that e-government was established for improving the provision and access of public services; however, it is

questionable whether it does improve access or worsens the existing inequalities in South African local government. The findings show that in rural areas, e-government services are not fully accessible, and this exacerbates inequalities. The paper shows the necessity for an inclusive electronic transition that is in line with Batho Pele principles of accountability, accessibility, and citizen-centred governance. To attain this, the paper recommends that the local government address technological as well as social gaps so e-government services benefit all community members. By doing so, the local government will translate into an inclusive and efficient government that offers e-government services that are equally accessible across South Africa.

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